

Oral Diseases Research Group
Ocho Oriente 1295
Talca, Chile
oraldiseases.org

Editor and reviewer certificate

Ref. cgv13092017

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.890799>.

This is to certificate that

Cristian González Villena

Has acted as an editor/reviewer for Mouth journal (ISSN 0719-7659) and is eligible for **10 hours of continuing professional development activities in 2016.**

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "César Rivera".

Signed: César Rivera orcid.org/0000-0002-5491-4233.
Editor-in-Chief, Mouth

Oral Diseases Research Group maintains a database of reviewers' and editors' activities for the purpose of recording continuing professional development.